

BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS ON FLEXOR HALLUCIS LONGUS REHABILITATION

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Keywords

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ABSTRACT

Aim: This study aims to conduct a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of research on flexor hallucis longus rehabilitation, identifying trends, influential studies, leading authors, and commonly used keywords. Methods: A bibliometric analysis was performed using the Web of Science database. Studies published between 2005 and 2025 were retrieved using the keywords "flexor hallucis longus" and terms related to balance, gait, falls, strength, exercise, training, and rehabilitation. Data were analyzed using VOSviewer software to visualize co-author networks, citation patterns, and keyword distributions. Results: A total of 145 studies met the inclusion criteria. The analysis revealed that the most cited authors are Flinkkila Tapio, Heikkinen Juuso, Laine Vesa, Lantto Iikka, and Leppilahti Juhana, respectively. The most cited country is the United States, with 261 citations. The most frequently used keyword is "flexor hallucis longus" (n=6), followed by "resistance training" (n=5), "biomechanics" (n=5), "gait" (n=4), and "Achilles tendon" (n=3). Conclusion: It is concluded that FHL plays a crucial role in the rehabilitation process, and international collaborations are essential for advancing scientific research in this field.

INTRODUCTION

The foot plays a critical role in human bipedalism with its unique structure. Extrinsic and intrinsic foot muscles work together to ensure proper coordination during various daily activities¹. As the only body part in direct contact with the ground during weight-bearing tasks, the foot provides body balance through its structure, posture, and muscle activity, transmitting and distributing impact forces. A significant portion of research on foot and ankle function focuses on the preservation of the foot arches through active, passive, and neural subsystems².

The Flexor Hallucis Longus (FHL), which plays a critical role in foot function, supports the medial longitudinal arch and helps with toe grip, especially during the push-off phase and on uneven surfaces. Located in the deep posterior compartment of the leg, the FHL originates from the fibula and attaches to the distal phalanx base of the big toe³. Its primary function is to flex the big toe; however, due to its crossing of the ankle joint, it also significantly contributes to plantar flexion force⁴. This function of the FHL has a great impact on balance and walking performance. Especially in older adults, the decrease in muscle strength weakens big toe function and foot support, which increases the risk of falls⁵. In many countries, aging and the increase in fall-related injuries among older individuals have become a growing public health issue⁶. Falls are the leading cause of death and injury among older individuals globally, second only to traffic accidents⁷. Strengthening the FHL can improve both big toe flexion and plantar flexion, positively affecting balance and walking performance⁸. This highlights the importance of FHL and its rehabilitation. Bibliometric analysis, through the qualitative and quantitative examination of scientific publications, helps to understand research trends and development boundaries⁹. By comparing contributions from different countries, institutions, journals, and researchers in this field, it provides valuable guidance for future studies¹⁰. A review of the literature reveals that bibliometric analyses focusing on FHL and related physiotherapy-rehabilitation terms (falls, walking, balance, exercise, etc.) are lacking. Specifically, there is a gap in holistic examinations regarding institutions, journals, authors, and keywords, as well as the discussion of the impact of these

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publications. Therefore, this study aims to provide a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of research on FHL, investigating the most productive countries, authors, the most cited studies, common keywords, and the bibliographic matching.

METHODS

In this section of the study, information is provided regarding the research design, data collection, and analysis of the collected data.

Research Design

In our study, research on FHL in the Web of Science (WoS) database was examined using the bibliometric analysis method. WoS is one of the most authoritative and comprehensive databases of scholarly materials worldwide and is frequently used for bibliometric analysis due to its rigorous indexing criteria and inclusion of high-impact journals, which is why we preferred it for our study.. Bibliometric analysis is a

method that involves the numerical evaluation of academic publications produced on a specific topic within a certain time frame and region¹¹. This method includes various statistical and mathematical techniques that allow for the analysis of bibliographic data¹². Bibliometric analysis helps to understand the current state of a field by revealing citation relationships between academic journals and provides a comprehensive perspective on both established and emerging research topics. The data used in this analysis can be obtained from various academic citation indexes such as WoS and Scopus¹³.

Research Data

The research was gathered from the WoS database. When conducting the search in the WoS database, the keywords "flexor hallucis longus" and (("balance" or "gait" or "fall" or "strength") or ("exercise" or "training" or "rehabilitation")) were used. The search process for the studies covers works published between 2005-2025. The search query used in the WoS database is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. WoS database search expression

Selection of Studies

For the selection of studies in the WoS database, the following filters were applied: "Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-E)" index, "English" language, and "article" filters. As a result of this filtering process, a total of 145 articles published between 2005 and 2025 were used in this research.

Data Analysis

In this study, the data from 145 studies were evaluated using the bibliometric analysis method. Bibliometric analysis is a comprehensive examination method used to determine the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of scientific publications¹². During this process, the information obtained from various databases was analyzed to reveal relationships among academic works. The data obtained from the WoS database were transferred to the computer in (.txt) format and

then analyzed using the VOSviewer software. VOSviewer is an analysis tool used to create and visualize bibliometric networks between academic components such as researchers, journals, citations, and individual publications (VOSviewer, 2024).

FINDINGS

This section presents the findings obtained from the analysis of the research data, along with evaluations of these findings. During the interpretation of the data, comparisons were made in light of the current literature and inferences were drawn.

Co-Author Analysis

As a result of the co-author network analysis, a network map was created based on the criteria of at least one publication and at least one citation to identify the most connected and collaborative authors. This situation is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Co-author network analysis in the context of authorship

According to the analysis of the authors with the highest number of connections, it is observed that there are 17 authors grouped into 3 clusters with a total of 64 connections. Among the authors in the cluster, the top 10 authors with the most connections each have a total of 16 unit connections.

Citation Analysis of Authors

In the citation analysis of authors, the authors with at least one publication and one citation were evaluated to form a collaboration network. The authors with the highest number of citations were identified, and this is visualized in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Authors' citation analysis

An analysis conducted on 37 units that are related to each other revealed 4 clusters, 203 connections, and a total connection strength of 269. In terms of total connection strength, Edgerton Vr (n=32) and Finni T (n=32) are in the top two positions, but they are not among the top 10 authors with the most citations. According to the analysis, the most cited authors are, in order, Flinkkila Tapio, Heikkinen Juuso, Laine Vesa, Lantto Iikka, and Leppilahti Juhana, with each of them having 173 citations, making up the top five on the list.

Citation Analysis of Countries

To determine the citation networks of countries, a network

map was created based on the criteria of having at least one publication and one citation, as shown in Figure 4.

As a result of the analysis, 4 clusters, 203 connections, and a total connection strength of 269 were identified. In terms of total connection strength, the United States, Finland, and Norway occupy the top three positions. The countries with the most citations are the United States (261 citations), Finland (228 citations), Iran (90 citations), Germany (87 citations), and the United Kingdom (70 citations).

Figure 4. Citation network map of countries

Keyword Analysis

The keyword network map created through bibliometric analysis helps us understand which keywords are used in the research literature, which keywords are most preferred by

researchers, and what kind of network connections exist among these preferred keywords. The keyword network map resulting from the analysis of studies related to flexor hallucis longus rehabilitation terms in the WoS database is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Keywords network visualization map

As a result of the analysis, it was found that 175 different keywords were used regarding rehabilitation terms related to flexor hallucis longus. The network map shown in the figure was created based on publications that used at least one keyword. Accordingly, 83 nodes, 12 clusters, and 218 connections emerged, resulting in a total connection strength of 222.

The most frequently used keyword was "flexor hallucis longus" (n=6). Other commonly used keywords included "resistance training" (n=5), "biomechanics" (n=5), "gait" (n=4), and "achilles tendon" (n=3).

Bibliographic Coupling Analysis

Bibliographic coupling refers to a situation where different sources cite and reference the same work. Based on the criterion of receiving at least one citation, an analysis was

performed on 29 works that had relationships with each other. The analysis results revealed 7 clusters, 71 connections, and a total connection strength of 140, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Bibliographic Coupling Network Map of the Works

Distribution of Works by Year in Bibliographic Coupling Analysis

publications related to FHL and rehabilitation terms was 2019, as shown in Figure 7.

The analysis shows that the year with the highest number of

Figure 7. Distribution of Works by Year

Distribution of Works by Web of Science Categories

field of orthopedics in the Web of Science categories, as shown in Figure 8.

As a result of the analyses, it was observed that the studies on FHL and related rehabilitation terms are mostly related to the

Figure 8. Distribution of Works by Web of Science Categories

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to examine the international literature on FHL and related rehabilitation terms in the Web of Science (WoS) database, based on various parameters. To achieve this, bibliometric analysis techniques were used to examine parameters such as the most published authors, preferred keywords, most connected authors, the most cited publications, and the countries with the highest number of citations.

In international literature, the author with the most citations on FHL and related rehabilitation terms is Heikkinen Juuso and colleagues with their study titled "Soleus Atrophy Is Common After the Nonsurgical Treatment of Acute Achilles Tendon Ruptures: A Randomized Clinical Trial Comparing Surgical and Nonsurgical Functional Treatments". This study mentions the occurrence of hypertrophies in the flexor hallucis longus muscle following acute Achilles tendon ruptures¹⁴.

When examining the publications on FHL and related rehabilitation terms by country, the USA leads with 261 citations, followed by Finland with 228 citations and Iran with 90 citations. They are followed by Germany with 87 citations and the UK with 70 citations. Looking at future research on FHL in the context of the scientific contributions of the top three most cited countries, this can help in understanding the experiences in the field, identifying the challenges encountered, and evaluating the opportunities that arise. This provides an important opportunity to support the global development of FHL studies and strengthen international collaborations. Particularly, collaborating with countries leading in scientific production can expand the scope of FHL research and accelerate scientific progress in the field. Our analysis of FHL shows that the USA and Finland play a dominant role. In line with this information, it is important for researchers from countries other than the leading countries, such as the USA and Finland, to participate in scientific production on this subject. Researchers from other countries can make a more significant contribution to science by collaborating with researchers from the leading countries¹⁵.

In the keyword analysis, the term "flexor hallucis longus" is at the center, followed by "resistance training." The strong relationship between these two keywords highlights the importance of exercises aimed at strengthening the flexor

hallucis longus muscle. A study emphasized the importance of FHL strengthening training for balance and walking parameters¹⁶. Although the number of studies on FHL has generally increased in recent years, a decline in publications in this area has been observed after the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic. The bibliometric analysis results show that studies on FHL are mainly concentrated in the field of orthopedics, and this topic could be explored more comprehensively from the perspectives of rehabilitation and sports sciences.

Limitations of the Study

By utilizing VOSviewer, we conducted an analysis of the past two decades' advancements concerning FHL and related rehabilitation concepts, applying a bibliometric approach for the first time. However, this study has some limitations. First, the literature reviewed was exclusively sourced from Web of Science. While its timely updates, authority, and extensive coverage provided a robust dataset for our analysis, integrating additional databases could have revealed more relevant studies. Furthermore, the authors did not examine the PEDro Physiotherapy Evidence Database, and thus, potentially important studies available in that database were excluded from the analysis. Second, our research focused solely on English-language research and review articles, thereby excluding non-English publications and other document types, which might have led to gaps in our findings. Lastly, given the continuous growth of scientific literature, some recently published influential studies may not have been captured in our analysis.

CONCLUSION

This study offers a comprehensive perspective on research in the field of physical therapy and rehabilitation regarding FHL. The data obtained using bibliometric analysis techniques reveal the trends and basic tendencies of scientific production in this field. By identifying the role of FHL in the rehabilitation process, the countries where research has concentrated, and the relationships between keywords, valuable insights for future studies have been provided. Citation networks and co-citation analysis in the scientific literature highlight the importance of key references and international collaborations in this field. In this context, the results of the study provide guidance for future research on FHL and emphasize the importance of international collaboration.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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Author Contributions

HG: protocol, data collection, data analysis, data management, manuscript writing, manuscript editing.

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REFERENCES

1. Fanous J, Rice CL. Flexor Hallucis Longus And Tibialis Anterior: A Synergistic Relationship. *J Electromyogr Kinesiol.* 2025;80:102966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelekin.2024.102966>
2. Wang J, Wang Y, Zhou B, Wang L, Lai Z. Age-Related Reduction Of Foot Intrinsic Muscle Function And The Relationship With Postural Stability In Old Adults. *Clinical Interventions In Aging.* 2024;19:1005-1015. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CIA.S454068>
3. Hirsch BE. Anatomy of the foot. In: William R. Ledoux and Scott Telfer. *Foot and Ankle Biomechanics*; Elsevier. Cambridge p. 3-44. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-815449-6.00040-8>
4. Perry J, Burnfield J. Normal And Pathological Function. In: *Gait Analysis 2nd Edition*. CRC Press; Boca Raton: 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003525592>
5. Mickle KJ, Munro BJ, Lord SR, Menz HB, Steele JR. ISB Clinical Biomechanics Award 2009: Toe weakness and deformity increase the risk of falls in older people. *Clinical Biomechanics.* 2009;24,10,:787-791. doi: 10.1016/j.clinbiomech.2009.08.011.
6. Montero-Odasso M, Van Der Velde N, Martin FC, Petrovic M, Tan MP, Ryg J, et al. World Guidelines For Falls Prevention And Management For Older Adults: A Global Initiative. *Age Ageing.* 2022;51,9:afac205. doi: 10.1093/ageing/afac205
7. Uysal I, Dogrukoc ON, Golcuk Y, Ozden F, Ozkeskin M, Baser M, et al. Urinary Incontinence In Men With Stroke: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Medicina.* 2025;61,1:52. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina61010052>
8. Pirker W, Katzenschlager R. Gait Disorders In Adults And The Elderly: A Clinical Guide. *Wiener Klinische Wochenschrift.* 2017;129,3:81-95. doi: 10.1007/s00508-016-1096-4.
9. Wang H, Shi J, Shi S, et al. Bibliometric Analysis Of Chronic Heart Failure Progression. *Current Problems In Cardiology.* 2022;47:101213. doi:10.1016/j.cpcardiol.2022.101213.
10. Wilson M, Sampson M, Barrowman N, Doja A. Bibliometric Analysis Of Neurology Articles Published In General Medical Journals. *JAMA Network Open.* 2021;4:e215840. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.5840.
11. TUBITAK. Bibliyometrik analiz. 2024. <https://cabim.ulakbim.gov.tr/bibliyometrik-analiz/bibliyometrik-analiz-sikca-sorulan-sorular/>
12. Donthu N, Kumar S, Mukherjee D, Pandey N, Lim WM. How To Conduct A Bibliometric Analysis: An Overview And Guidelines. *Journal Of Business Research.* 2021;133:285-296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.070>
13. Tamala JK, Maramag E, Simeon KA, Ignacio JJ. A Bibliometric Analysis Of Sustainable Oil And Gas Production Research Using Vosviewer. *Cleaner Engineering And Technology* 2022;7:1-9. DOI: 10.1016/j.clet.2022.100437
14. Heikkinen J, Lantto I, Flinkkila T, Ohtonen P, Niinimäki J, Siira P, Et Al. Soleus Atrophy Is Common After The Nonsurgical Treatment Of Acute Achilles Tendon Ruptures: A Randomized Clinical Trial Comparing Surgical And Nonsurgical Functional Treatments. *The American Journal Of Sports Medicine.* 2017;45,6,:1395-1404. Doi: 10.1177/0363546517694610. Epub 2017 Mar 10.
15. Ates A, Unsal H. Bibliometric Analysis Of Studies On Flipped Learning. *Turkish Journal Of Education Science.* 2024;22,2:1084-1098. <https://doi.org/10.37217/tebd.1489685>
16. Rowley KM, Jarvis DN, Kurihara T, Chang YJ, Fietzer AL, Kulig K. Toe Flexor Strength, Flexibility And Function And Flexor Hallucis Longus Tendon Morphology In Dancers And Non-Dancers. *Medical Problems Of Performing Artists.* 2015;30,3: 152-156. Doi: 10.21091/Mppa.2015.3029.